

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ATTITUDES OF YOUNG FAMILIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the social characteristics of the transformation of the institution of the family. The results of sociological surveys and statistical data on the example of families in Uzbekistan are presented. In order to resolve and prevent family problems, appropriate recommendations were proposed.*

Key words: *family, divorce, types of transformation, socio-psychological characteristics, family nuclearity, multigeneration, psychological assistance to the family.*

In Uzbekistan, strengthening the family is a priority task of the state.

The problem of families is one of the most pressing issues. But the negative consequences of family relationships often become a problem not only for the family, but also for society. Divorces are an acute social problem.

As the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "Unfortunately, there are cases when young families do not have a clear idea of family life and do not understand that the family is sacred. Divorces are growing among young families. As a result, children become orphans, are left outside the care of their parents, when they most crave parental warmth and attention."

The family is a microcosm of the whole world. To understand it, it is enough to know the family. Manifestations of power, intimacy, independence, trust, communication skills that exist in it are the key to unraveling many phenomena of life. If we want to change the world, we need to change the family." The family is called upon to create an atmosphere of love and closeness for each member, thereby protecting from anxiety and stress. A person places responsibility on the family for gaining self-confidence, a feeling of being loved and appreciated [1].

The problem of the family is a pressing issue for all countries and at all times, regardless of the ethnoculture, socio-economic development and historical period.

This statement is due to the following:

- the family (parents) serve as the most important source of inheritance of a certain genetic program, which largely determines the psychophysical development, formation and realization of the individual;

- the family is the most important factor in the socialization of the individual, the source of moral and spiritual development of a person;

- the features of the institution of the family are subject to the influence of the socio-economic development of society, urbanization, educational and cultural level of its members, ideology, religion and historical stage of development;

- the results of the study of the family in one ethnoculture cannot be applied to another ethnoculture, etc.

It is known that the family is the primary unit and an important social institution of society [1, p. 23]. Among the classification of families, it is the young family that is distinguished by its socio-psychological characteristics, attitudes, and views on the future. It should be noted that a

young family is a family in which the age of both spouses does not exceed thirty years inclusive. This family is at the stage of forming new relationships (interpersonal and intrafamily), a new status (the status of a daughter-in-law, young parents), a new economic situation (financial security of a young family, personal financial resources), new life guidelines. [3, p. 16].

According to statistics, there are currently approximately 9.3 million families in Uzbekistan, 3.2 million of which are young families. A young family is always the focus of our state's attention.

A young family and harmoniously developed youth should become the basis of all reforms in Uzbekistan, implement innovative ideas, solutions and actions. The implementation of state policy in the republic in the sphere of innovative development, education, strengthening the institution of the family requires special attention to youth issues, their spiritual and moral education, and comprehensive development.

In 2021-2023, we conducted a socio-psychological study among young families. A total of 2837 respondents took part in the survey, of which 31.6% were men and 62.8% were women.

The survey was conducted in the Uzbek language in the form of an interview. The sample population is representative. The selection of respondents is proportional to the population in the regions (it should be noted that there are 14 regions in the republic) with coverage of 5-9% of the population in each region.

As is known, the characteristics of a young family have changed over the past two decades [2, p. 36].

The change of priorities in the development of the republic in connection with the transition to market relations contributed to the change of stereotypes, moral norms of young families, their values in the family.

The compiled portrait of a young family showed that young families in most cases live in an official marriage, registered in the civil registry office and secured by a religious ceremony. Of these, 80% have children (37% - 1 child, 32% - 2 children, 11% - 3 or more children).

Everyone knows that the age of marriage is a factor in the stability of families. Early marriages, as a rule, become one of the reasons for divorce in young families. According to the survey results, about 70% of respondents got married at the age of 18-27. Among girls, 6% got married at 17 and earlier, among guys, 41% got married after 27.

In accordance with the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the marriage age is set for men at eighteen years, for girls at seventeen years. In exceptional cases (pregnancy, birth of a child), the Mayor (khokim) of the district, city at the place of state registration of marriage may, at the request of persons wishing to marry, reduce the marriage age, but not more than by one year. Since 2019, an amendment has been made to set the marriage age for those getting married the same from eighteen years. Most young people believe that one should get married at 21-27 years old.

Living together with parents has a positive effect on the level of well-being of a young family, since parents take an active part in running the household and raising children. According to the survey results, more than half of the respondents answered that they live with their parents, 26% have their own housing and 6% live in rented apartments. At the same time, 18% of respondents noted that they live with their parents due to the lack of their own housing and would like to live separately from their parents. About 18% found it difficult to answer this question. For 26% of young families living with parents, living together is convenient, since parents provide them with all possible assistance in everyday life and raising children, and for 29%, living together

with parents is a moral duty to them. To the question of who makes decisions in everyday life and manages the family budget, the following was noted: "young family" - 45.0%; "parents" - 50.0%; "together" - 5.0%. The intensity of parents' help in everyday life depends on whether they work or not. In a modern family, working pensioners continue to work in order to provide financial assistance to young people and create favorable conditions, especially in the first years of a young family's life and during the birth of a child.

Research by Uzbek scientists shows that nuclear families are typical for Uzbekistan, i.e. families consisting of two parents and their children - 58.1%. The number of nuclear families has been decreasing in recent years, while the number of multi-generational families has been growing. By definition, a multi-generational family is a family consisting of parents, children and grandparents. Considering the fact that some of the child-rearing responsibilities are taken on by older people, living with grandparents can be considered a positive factor in the formation of a full-fledged younger generation. Satisfaction of young families with their lives determines the stability of relationships and the future of the family. Based on this, we included the question in the questionnaire: "How satisfied are you with your life?" In general, most young families are satisfied with their situation: 58.9% - "completely satisfied", 32.7% - "partially satisfied" and 8.4% - "not satisfied".

In order to effectively solve the problems of young families, it is proposed:

1. To form in children from an early age ideas about family, family traditions and individual aspects of life together by studying the foundations of the family in educational institutions, in institutions of personal socialization.

2. To improve mutual understanding between newlyweds and to form a favorable socio-psychological climate in the family, it is necessary to organize methods and ways of family education.

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